

EuroMix

European Test and Risk Assessment Strategies for Mixtures

Project number 633172

Collaborative project
H2020-SFS-2014-2

Deliverable D10.1 – Website

Website for EuroMix project

WP 10 – Dissemination and stakeholder involvement

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Dissemination Level		
PU	Public	X
PP	Restricted to other programme participants (including the Commission)	
RE	Restricted to a group specified by the consortium (including the Commission)	
CO	Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission)	

Deliverable D10.1

Website for EuroMix project

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Deliverable 10.1

Website for EuroMix project

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Summary

The EuroMix project website was set out to be a multifaceted website with; 1) A public platform with general information about the project's approach, objectives, results and methodology 2) A private platform for partners, where the relevant project documents, drafts, etc. can be presented for consultation and discussion.

The following actions have been fulfilled:

- Logo
- Draft design/layout, menus
- Management system of the Website – Wordpress and Pydio
- First content of website
- Launching of website, 3rd of July 2015 – www.euromixproject.eu

A tiered strategy for risk assessment of mixtures of multiple chemicals

Project

Every day, we are exposed to multiple chemicals by several routes of exposure: diet, inhalation and dermal contact. These chemicals may exert toxic effects and therefore risk assessment by evaluation of exposure and toxicity is necessary to monitor and control possible adverse effects on human health. Until recently, risk assessment is mostly performed separately for each chemical, considering only a single route of exposure. However, this simplified risk assessment does not take into account the effect that chemicals may have on each other and their effect on the target organ, such as synergistic effects of certain chemicals with a particular toxic effect, in case of co-exposure. Therefore, there is a need to address combined exposure to mixtures of chemicals and their combined risks as set out in EU Regulation.

There are, however, thousands of chemicals, and their contribution to the combined risk depends on the toxic profile of the chemical(s) together with the level to which the consumer is exposed to these chemicals. The main issue here is how to prioritise the chemicals to be tested, how to test new chemicals for their synergistic effects and how to group chemicals in a proper way for appropriate risk assessment allowing refinement wherever needed. Whereas in traditional toxicological effects of single chemicals are tested using animal experiments, the societal need for reducing animal testing and cost-effective toxicology testing calls for *in-vitro* and *in-silico* strategies. Therefore, the main objective of EuroMix is to develop an experimentally verified, tiered test strategy for risk assessment of mixtures of chemicals from different sources.

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All partners have received access to the private platform and can login to the Shared EuroMix site with Username and Password. Access to the public platform is restricted to the coordinating partner and the WP10 leader.